

A Perspective to Understand Emotional Design

Extending of Design Methods with Inherent Knowledge

SuKyoung Kim * Kazuhisa Niki ** and Toshimasa Yamanaka ***

* *Doctoral program in Kansei, Behavioral and Brain Sciences, Graduate School of Comprehensive Human Sciences, University of Tsukuba, Tsukuba, Japan, sukyoung.rainbow@gmail.com*

** *Human Life Technology, National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology Tsukuba, Japan, k.niki@aist.go.jp*

*** *Graduate School of Comprehensive Human Sciences, University of Tsukuba, Tsukuba, Japan, tyam@geijutsu.tsukuba.ac.jp*

Abstract: Most products contain inherent images as well as intended images. While the influence of intended shapes on product evaluation has been well studied, the influence of inherent images remains unexplored. Thus, this study investigated the influence of inherent images on products. There were 20 subjects in two consecutive experimental sessions: 1) evaluation item screening, and 2) affective evaluation. In the first session, the subjects made decisions within the limited time in regards to their preference on the stimuli. In the second session, the subjects evaluated the stimuli with SAM (Self Assessment Manikin), which selected by their preference. SAM (Self Assessment Manikin) is an efficient measurement of emotional responses: valence, arousal, and dominance. In the study, car front images were used as stimuli on the similar disposition towards human face expression. Results showed that: 1) products contain inherent images that trigger affective differences; 2) arousal was the most affective value in inherent images.

Key words: *Design Methods, Metaphor, Subliminal, Emotion, Decision-making.*

1. Introduction

Inherent information is not easy to express in words the consumers as well as designers or marketers. Considering the central tenet of Gestalt psychology, the whole is different from the sum of its parts. Gestalt, by definition, is derived from a “pattern” or “shape,” although “configuration” comes closer to its intended meaning in German. Furthermore, the Gestalt theory plays a role by considering human face perception in products as well as in abstract ways [Figure. 1]. Product form is one way to gain consumer notice [1-3]. Also, form or exterior appearance of a product is important as a means of communicating to consumers [4]. Product form can have long lasting effects. Morality is more properly felt than judged [5]. This study was built on with the background as follows.

The human face is a complex multi-signal system from which we can infer a great deal of information at no more than a glance – in other words, after only 100 ms of exposure [6]. Such information is encoded and perceived in car fronts [7]. Also, the idea that cars have faces has been proposed [8], and has been investigated systematically [9]. It has been noted in many face perception research studies that people reliably and automatically make personality inferences from facial expression despite little evidence for their accuracy. Because of that a facial expression is a silent social signal, influencing mate choice and other social judgment.

Figure.1

It has been found that a happy or angry face influenced the likeability of a visual target only when the face was displayed subliminally [10]. Also, it is widely accepted that unconscious processes can modulate judgments and behavior. Car front faces were metaphorically related to the human face, which can be understood by ideas based on metaphor theory. Metaphor is a device for seeing something in terms of something else [11]. In other words, metaphor is the way we understand new things to conceive of them in terms of things we already know. Therefore, metaphor within products can be a powerful tool for conceptualizing, orienting, and personifying products [12]. Face perception evoked activation in a distributed network that included regions in the visual cortex, limbic system, prefrontal cortex, and reward circuitry [13]. In contrast, to the authors' knowledge, no study has examined the subliminal choice focus on the human face perception in product design.

In Kansei research that considers both rational and also emotional aspects that human have, emotional values are important on its process. Kansei is usually described as a mental function, and more precisely as being a higher function of the brain. The literature indicates, Kansei process gathers the functions related to emotion, sensitivity, feelings, experience, and intuition, including interactions between them [14]. In this research, the authors focused on three emotional values: Valence, Arousal, and Dominance, which affect the Kansei process.

2. Method

2.1. Subjects

All subjects were native Japanese. They were 20 (7 females) undergraduate and graduate students (13 males and 7 females, aged from 21 to 29 years, $M= 24.1$, $SD=2.69$). No subjects had previously experienced stimuli or evaluation. None of the subjects was in an automotive-related major.

2.2. Materials

One hundred thirty-nine models representing thirty-five brands varied in car front images were used. The images were taken from copyright-free Internet sites and photograph collections. Also, no stimulus was selected

on intention, such as brand, model, and producer. One hundred thirty-nine models that varied in car front faces were selected from thirty-five brands. All categories; sedan, coupe, convertible, pickup, SUV, hatchback, minivan, wagon, full-sized van, and classic, were included. The perspective of automotive front pictures was the same: the front of its car [Figure 2]. Only quality of the images was considered. All pictures were filtered in gray scale to avoid from color effect. License plates were erased, although brand logos were retained. Finally, all the pictures were rendered at 580*370 pixels. The experiment screen was at 550*500 pixels. No specific background used.

Figure.2 The example of the stimuli

2.3. Procedure

Using a within-subject design, each subject was assigned to two whole tasks. A within-subject design was used to compare the independent variables within a subject. In this study, it was adapted to investigate the relation of preference and affective values within a subject. The experimental procedure was as follows: first, the subjects were given general instruction and informed that the purpose of the experiment was to investigate the relation between preference and affective values with car fronts. All instructions were in Japanese because of all subjects were Japanese.

The procedure that subjects followed was for item screening first, and rating each selected stimuli by subjects themselves consecutively. In the item screening session, the preferences scale - like or dislike - was adopted as contribute to the research, considering the most subliminal-related descriptor form previous studies. In addition, since time limitation was used to interrupt the rational thinking process of the rater, it applied pressure to the subjects by giving them limited time. They carried out the pre-task 2 times before conducting every task to adapt to tasks. Pre-task stimuli were used in different ways from the main-tasks. With the item screening session, the 5 most-preferred and the 5 least-preferred car front images were screened by the selected time priority. In the affective evaluation session, the subject was instructed in detail to make the ratings using the subjective states, due to lake of familiarity with the SAM scale by Japanese participants. The subjects were given the following explanation:

You can see that each SAM figure varies along each scale. In this illustration, the first SAM scale is the happy-unhappy scale, which ranges from a smile to a frown. At one extreme of the happy vs. unhappy scale, you felt happy, pleased, satisfied, contented, hopeful. If you felt completely happy while viewing the picture, you can indicate this by placing a mark over the figure at the left, like this (demonstrate with SAM on the screen). The other end of the scale

is when you felt completely unhappy, annoyed, unsatisfied, melancholic, despaired, bored. You can indicate feeling completely unhappy by placing a mark on the figure at the right, like this (demonstrate with SAM on the screen). The figures also allow you to describe intermediate feelings of pleasure, by placing the slider over any of the other pictures. If you felt completely neutral, neither happy nor unhappy, place a mark over the figure in the middle. If, in your judgment, your feeling of pleasure or displeasure falls between two of the pictures, then place a mark between the figures, like this (demonstrate with SAM on the screen). This permits you to make more finely graded ratings of how you feel in reaction to the pictures.

The excited vs. calm dimension is the second type of feeling displayed here. At one extreme of the scale you felt stimulated, excited, frenzied, jittery, wide-awake, aroused. If you felt completely aroused while viewing the picture, place a mark over the figure at the left of the row, like this (demonstrate with SAM). On the other hand, at the other end of the scale, you felt completely relaxed, calm, sluggish, dull, sleepy, unaroused. You can indicate you felt completely calm by placing a mark over the figure at the right of the row, like this (demonstrate with SAM on the screen). As with the happy-unhappy scale, you can represent intermediate levels by placing a mark over any of the other figures. If you are not at all excited nor at all calm, place a mark over the figure in the middle of the row. Again, if you wish to make a more finely tuned rating of how excited or calm you feel, place the slider between the pictures, like this (demonstrate with SAM on the screen).

The last scale of feeling that you will rate is the dimension of controlled vs. in-control. A one end of the scale you have feelings characterized as completely controlled, influenced, cared for, awed, submissive, guided. Please indicate feeling controlled by placing a mark over the figure at the left, like this (demonstrate with SAM on the screen). At the other extreme of this scale, you felt completely controlling, influential, in control, important, dominant, autonomous. You can indicate that you felt dominant by placing a mark over the figure at the right of the row, like this (demonstrate with SAM on the screen). Note that when the figure is large, you feel important and influential, and that it will be very small when you feel controlled and guided. If you feel neither in control nor controlled you should make a mark over the middle picture. Remember you can also represent your feelings between these endpoints. Either place the slider over any of the intermediate figures, or between them--like this (demonstrate with SAM on the screen).

We used an event related design also, in which images were displayed in counter-balance. Therefore it was unpredictable. The subjects should mark all 3 dimensions to show how they felt while looking at the photographs. Also, the subject was reminded that there are no right or wrong answers.

3. Results

The values in the 3 dimensions were as follows:

1. In **Valence** (happy vs. unhappy): More preferred car front images gave happier feelings than less preferred car front images. However, it did not show significance ($p < 1.138$) [Table 1].

2. In **Arousal** (excited vs. calm): More preferred car front images gave more exciting feeling than less preferred car front images. Also, it showed significance ($p < 0.009$) [Tables 1].
3. In **Dominance** (controlled vs. in-control): More preferred automotive front images gave more in-control feeling than less preferred car front images. However, it did not show significance ($p < 0.562$) [Table 1].

Accordingly, only the value in **Arousal** (excited vs. calm) showed significance. The means of less preferred car front images showed much stronger reactions in more preferred car front images (-1.26) than less preferred car front images (0.28). Also, the results showed that exciting car fronts were more preferred than the calmative-giving car front images [Table 1]. Also, on **Dominance** (controlled vs. in-control), it showed that in-control feelings more preferred than controlled feeling.

Table 1. The means of SAM rating in the 3 dimensions, and the p values

	Valence (happy vs. unhappy)	Arousal (excited vs. calm)	Dominance (controlled vs. in-control)
The means of	Like (more preferred): -1.26 Dislike (less preferred): 0.28	Like : -0.23 Dislike : 0.4	Like : 0.15 Dislike : 0
p value	<1.138	<0.009	<0.562

4. Discussions & Conclusions

Are consumers really able to choose what is best for them? Many psychologists suspect that we do not make choices that maximize our happiness. Consumers fail to choose optimally, either because they fail to predict accurately, or to base their choice, or both [15]. It inferred that failed choices could be more related to cognitive process, i.e., prediction or memory, than subliminal. Based on the inferences, the authors investigated the relationship between unconscious choice and subsequent emotional values, such as pleasure, arousal, and dominance.

The results showed that (1) there was the relation between preference and the emotional values, despite the interruption by imposing time limits, (2) also, the arousal value showed the statistical significance in preference on car front images [Table 1]. It inferred that the arousal value is more considerable to understand individuals' preferences with "silent social signal," even though it was not clear whether the Wundt curve worked in this research. Considering the results, just little exciting - not neutral arousal like as in the Wundt curve - car front images were preferred, and little calmatives were not preferred. It could require further research to confirm whether the research follows the Wundt curve.

According to previous research, arousal influences recall in a positive way by its increasing the secretion of epinephrine. In turn, the epinephrine will "push" short-term memory into long-term memory in the brains [16-17]. In this condition, the assumption is that there is already something existing in the short-term memory area of

the brains. Therefore, high arousal consumers will remember the subliminal message better than lower arousal consumers. On the contrary, researchers who argued that arousal interfere with message recall based their argument on the mechanism that the high arousal condition distracts consumers' attention [18], such that an individual cannot contemplate and remember well without enough cognition resources. Several researchers in psychology [19-21] have examined the relationship between arousal and subsequent processing of information and decision making. Their results suggest that higher arousal levels in individuals would lead to lower approach behaviors (or increased avoidance behaviors) in subsequent tasks. Mano (1992) found that subjects experiencing higher levels of arousal spent less time deliberating on subsequent decision tasks, examined less decision-related information and employed simpler decision strategies [20]. These researchers accounted for this effect with a cognitive processing explanation that more arousing stimuli elicit more attention and more elaborate network encoding in memory than less arousing stimuli [e.g., 22]. This restricts the attention and processing resources that can be allocated to subsequent tasks, so that more aroused subjects tend to simplify future decisions and avoid more stimulating contexts compared to less aroused subjects. Also, emotions represent motivational phenomena with characteristic neurophysiological, expressive and experiential components [23].

Emotive response is both psychological and physiological in nature, generating altered states in both the mind and body. It includes but extends beyond the affect or preference variables often studied by marketing researchers. Arousal is defined as the level of alertness or activation on a continuum ranging from extreme drowsiness to extreme wakefulness. This research is on the process to propose new design methods with both learned and inherent sensibilities. In the research, the authors focused on the inherent sensibilities, which related to subliminal choice. With the research, the prospect for future research is to look closely; arousal will be of considerable value for understanding what consumers' latent desires to design with their inherent sensitivities. The remaining questions are: 1) to confirm whether cognitive choices make differences as in this experiment, which limited the process; 2) to confirm whether the research follows the Wundt curve. Further, incorporating proofs based on neuroscience with our research would allow even more interesting conclusions, such as related to the reports that face perception evoked activation in a distributed network that included regions in the visual cortex, limbic system, prefrontal cortex, and reward circuitry [24]. Also, comparison of time-limited choice and non-limited free time choice in arousal feeling choice remains an open question considering activation-evoking of reward circuitry in the brain.

5. References

- [1] Berkowitz, J. (1987). Products Shape as a Design Innovation Strategy. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 4, 274-83.
- [2] Dumaine, B. (1991). "Design that Sells and Sells and ..." *Fortune*, 11, 86-94.
- [3] Johns, P. L. (1991). *Taste Today*. New York: Pergamon Press.
- [4] Nussbaum, B. (1988). Smart Design. *Business Week*, 11, (pp. 102-17).
- [5] Hume, D. (1997). *Of the Origin of Government*. In Muller, J. Z. (Ed.), *Conservatism* (p. 36). Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- [6] Willis, J. & Todrov, A. (2006). First impressions: Making up your mind after a 100-ms exposure to a face. *Psychological Sciences*, 17, 592-598.

- [7] Desmet, P. M. A., Hekkert, P. & Jacobs, J. J. (2000). When a car makes you smile: Development and application of an instrument to measure product emotions, In S. J. Hoch & R. J. Mayer (Eds.). *Advances in Consumer Research*, 27, (pp. 111-117). Provo, UT: Association for Consumer Research.
- [8] Erk, S., Spitzer, M., Wunderlich, A. P., Gallary, L. & Walter, H. (2002). Cultural objects modulate reward circuitry. *Neuro Report*, 13, 2499-2503.
- [9] Windhager, S., Slice, D. E., Schaefer, K., Oberzaucher, E., Thorstensen, T. & Grammer, K. (2008). Face to face: The perception of Automotive Designs. *Human Nature*, DOI 10.1007/s12110-008-9047-z.
- [10] Murphy, S. T. & Zajonc, R. B. (1993). Affect, cognition, and awareness: Affective priming with optimal and suboptimal stimulus exposures. *Journal of social Psychology*, 64, 723-739.
- [11] Burke, K. (1945). *A Grammar of Motives and a Rhetoric of Motives*. Berkeley, Los Angeles, London: University of California Press.
- [12] Saffer, D. (2005). The Role of metaphor in Interaction Design (Unpublished Master thesis in Interactive Design, The school of Design). Carnegie Mellon University.
- [13] Karants, F., Ishai, A. (2006). Face perception is modulated by sexual preference. *Current Biology*, 16, 63-69.
- [14] Levy, P. & Yamanaka, T. (2009). Kansei studies Description and Mapping through Kansei Studies Keywords. *Kansei Engineering International*, 8 (2), 179-185.
- [15] Hsee, C. K. & Hastie, R. (2006). Decision and experience: why don't we choose what makes us happy? *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 10 (1), 31-37.
- [16] Russell, J. A. & Barrett, L. F. (1999). Core affect, prototypical emotional episodes, and other things called emotion: Dissecting the elephant. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 76(5), 805-819.
- [17] Merikle, P. M. (2000). Subliminal perception. In Kazdin, A. E. (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Psychology*, 7, (pp. 497-499). New York: Oxford University Press.
- [18] Clore, G. L. & Schnall, S. (2005). The influence on affect on attitude. In Albarracín, D., Johnson, B. T., and Zanna, M. P. (Eds), *The Handbook of Attitudes*, 11, (pp. 437-488). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Inc.
- [19] Singh, S. & Hitchon, J. (1989). The intensifying effects of exciting television programs on the reception of subsequent commercials. *Psychology and Marketing*, 6, 1-31.
- [20] Kahneman, D. (1973). *Attention and effort*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- [21] Mano, H. (1992). Judgments under distress: assessing the role of unpleasantness and arousal in judgment formation. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 52, 216-245.
- [22] Sanbonmatsu, D. M. & Kardes, F. R. (1988). The effects of physiological arousal on information processing and persuasion, *Journal of Consumer Research*, 15, 379-385.

- [23] Izard, C. E. & Buechler, S. (1980). Aspects of Consciousness and Personality in Terms of Differential Emotions. In Plutchik, R. & Kellerman, H. (Eds.), *Theory, in Emotion, Research and Experience*, 1, (pp. 165-187). New York: Academic Press.
- [24] Humphreys, M. S. & Revelle, W. (1984). Personality, Motivation, and Performance: A Theory of the Relationship Between Individual Differences and Information Processing, *Psychological Review*, 91, 153-184.